

Yield and yield attributes of rice as affected by seedling age and rate of Zn application. Nainital, India, 1988 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Filled grain percentage	1000-grain weight (g)
Seedling age (d)					
30	6.7	197	131	90.3	29.0
40	6.2	194	127	91.2	29.2
50	5.7	182	122	86.5	28.7
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.2	6	2	1.9	0.4
Zn rate (ppm)					
0	5.9	180	111	87.3	28.1
1	5.9	184	118	87.8	28.7
2	6.2	190	127	89.1	28.9
4	6.4	197	132	90.1	29.4
8	6.7	208	148	92.7	29.8
Spray	6.0	189	122	88.9	28.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	6	4	1.5	1.1

treatments, but 1,000-grain weight was not.

The interaction between seedling age and Zn rate was not significant. □

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Disease management

A new sheath disease of rice in India caused by *Monographella albescens*

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From Oct 1986 onward, we observed a severe sheath disease of rice in MAC experimental plots and in many farmers' fields.

The lesions develop as oblong or irregular spots 1-2 cm long and 0.5-1.0 cm wide with dark brown margins and greyish centers. About 80-100% of uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing young panicles are rotted. Many small, black, fruiting bodies (perithecia) of *M. albescens* appear on infected sheaths and grains.

We isolated the pathogen from fresh diseased specimen on potato dextrose agar. It produced white mycelium during early growth. At maturity, it produced pink patches of conidial masses. We inoculated the injured sheaths with conidial suspension prepared from a 7-d-old culture. Symptoms appeared 4 d after inoculation. In 2 wk, uppermost leaf sheaths and young panicles completely

rotted. Several superficial, black perithecia were formed.

Microscopic examination showed morphological characteristics exactly the same as those of leaf scald (LSc) pathogen. The anamorph and teleomorph have been identified as *Gerlachia oryzae* (Hashioka and

Yokogi), *W. Gams* and *M. albescens* (Thiimen) Parkinson, Sivanesan, and Booth, respectively. The anamorph of the LSc pathogen was previously reported in India, but the teleomorph has evidently not been. This indicates that the same fungus can produce different disease symptoms. □

Improved method of purifying rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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We improved the method of purifying RTSV without using organic solvent and driselase:

Infected TN plants at 45-60 d

Harvest whole plants except roots.

Homogenize in 3 volumes of 0.01 M EDTA, pH 8.4.

Filter through cheesecloth.

Filtrate

Stir at room temperature for 2 h.

Incubate in water bath at 40 °C for 2 h.

15,000 g for 10 min.

Supernatant

Add PEG 8000 to 7%, NaCl to 0.2M and Triton X-100 to 1%.

Stir at room temperature for 1 h.

30,000 g for 30 min.

Pellet

Resuspend in 20 ml 0.01 M EDTA, pH 8.4.

11,000g for 10 min.

Supernatant

100,000 g for 60 min.

Pellet

Resuspend in 2 ml 0.01 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. 11,000 g for 10 min.

Supernatant

Layer on 10-50% linear sucrose density gradient in PB.

25,000 rpm for 2 h.

Collect a virus zone (ca. 3 cm below the meniscus).

Dilute with 0.01 PB.

130,000 g for 1 h.

Pellet

Resuspend in 2 ml 0.01 PB. 11,000 g for 10 min.

Supernatant (virus preparation)